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Executive Summary

This document is a proposal by the WP leader for a set of rules, guidelines and recommendations, which apply, to all development and customisation activities within WP 34.

1. Purpose of this document

This document defines the guidelines, rules and recommendations that have to be followed or considered when developing, adapting or integrating software components for the CRISMA Framework. This includes e.g., how APIs are specified and implemented or which technologies are used for the development of composite UI modules, how composite UI modules communicate and interact, etc. Several rules have already been formulated on conceptual level in Functional Architecture of the CRISMA Framework (D32.1, chapter “Concepts”). A few rules have been described on a more technical level in the draft of Implementation Architecture of the CRISMA Framework (D32.1, chapter “Implementation”).

Parts of this document will eventually become part of the upcoming deliverables D32.2 and D34.1.

1.1. Conventions

The keywords "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC 2119 (RFC2119).

The terms "JSON", "JSON text", "JSON value", "member", "element", "object", "array", "number", "string", "boolean", "true", "false", and "null" in this document are to be interpreted as defined in RFC 4627 (RFC4627).

2. General rules for CRISMA Federates

The following chapter provides a summary of rules for CRISMA Federates that were introduced by the CRISMA Framework Architecture (D32.1, 2013).

2.1. Rules for CRISMA Federates

Those are the basic rules for CRISMA Federates that are needed to guarantee and support interaction, interoperability and integration within CRISMA Federations and CRISMA Applications.

1. A CRISMA Federate must be aware of the APIs of the CRISMA Middleware Infrastructure (ICMM) and the related core Control and Communication Information Models (CCIM).
2. A CRISMA Federate may but does not have to expose a dedicated RESTful CRISMA API that is aligned to the APIs of the ICMM.
3. Control and Communication Information shall not be exchanged between Federates directly. It must be transferred solely using the APIs provided by the Middleware Infrastructure (ICMM).
4. The mandatory communication protocol used in communication with the ICMM is the hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP).
5. CRISMA Federates may exchange data with non-CRISMA components (Integrated Components).
6. The preferred protocol for the exchange of data is HTTP.
7. The preferred method for direct data transfer is based upon open standards and services of the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC).
8. Integrated Components are not aware of the ICMM API but may take part in an interaction of CRISMA Federates.
9. A CRISMA Federation must be composed of CRISMA Federates only.
10. An existing software component that wants to join a CRISMA Federation and thus become a CRISMA Federate has to be aware of the ICMM API and thus must be able to exchange Control and Communication Information with the ICMM.
11. A CRISMA Application may be composed of CRISMA Federates, Integrated Components, Integrated Simulation Models and Integrated Systems

2.2. Rules for CRISMA Building Blocks

In addition to the general rules for Federates, CRISMA Building Blocks have to adhere to the following rules:

1. CRISMA Building Blocks are Federates that are provided by the CRISMA Framework developed in SP3.
2. CRISMA Framework Building Blocks must be composable and configurable, and thus adaptable to the needs and requirements of the CRISMA Application (Pilot Applications) to be built.

2.3. Rules for Federated Simulations and Simulation Models

The following rules apply to Federated Simulations and Federated or Integrated Simulation Models.

Figure 1: Examples for Federated Simulations

1. According to the mutually agreed model integration approach, any **federated** simulation model must be provided as OGC Web Processing Service (WPS)
2. Input and output data of federated simulation models should be provided via OGC service such as SOS, WFS and WMS.

3. A Federated Simulation may be composed of one or more Federated or Integrated Simulations models but appears itself as Federated Simulation Model and thus is accessible via one OGC WPS interface.
4. Any simulation model shall be able to provide a human readable description of its purpose.
5. Any simulation model shall be able to provide information about the supported, required and optional parameters that have to be available in order to perform a new model run. This includes information how this data can be provided, e.g. if it can be transmitted prior to the actual execution request and where it shall reside, if it shall be part of the actual execution request, if the actual execution request may contain links to the actual data. Additionally it must state what formats and encodings are supported for each parameter as well as being able to provide validity range if applicable.
6. Any simulation model shall be able to provide meta-information about its result data. This includes information on supported data formats and means for retrieving the data (Example: the result of a run is map raster data and can be fetched at a specific WMS using a certain URL).
7. Any simulation model shall be able to provide information about the status of a specific execution (simulation run). Requesters may be informed at any time whether an execution is Scheduled, Running, Paused, Failed, or Finished.
8. Any simulation model shall be able to either indicate the expected execution time for a certain run and the remaining execution time or at least provide an indication of the actual status.
9. Any simulation model shall be able to provide detailed error messages e.g. in case of a failed execution

3. Rules Building Block Implementations

The following rules cover the adaptation of existing software components and the implementation of new Building Blocks from scratch.

3.1. Rules for Software Candidates

Software Candidates are software components that are selected and adapted for the realisation of a certain CRISMA Framework Building Blocks.

1. A candidate software component for a Building Block Implementation must be made CRISMA-aware, which means that it exchanges events and Control and Communication Information with the CRISMA Middleware Infrastructure (ICMM).
2. The user interface(s) of a software component that is a candidate for Building Block implementation should be exposed as Composite UI Modules that can be either integrated into other GUIs (with help of the UI Integration Platform Building Block) or put together with other Composite UI Modules to a rich internet application (with help of the UI Mashup Platform Building Block).
3. If for technical reasons the user interface(s) of the candidate software component cannot be provided as Composite UI Modules a mechanism must be provided that allows the integration of other Composite UI Modules into the native GUI of the software component (with help of the UI Integration Platform Building Block).
4. A candidate software component should offer its programmatically accessible functionality; this is functionality that can be accessed by other software components; through a well-defined interface that must be realised as HTTP RESTful API.

3.2. Rules for Building Block Implementation

Those are general rules for the implementation of Building Blocks.

1. Building Block Software Components shall be generic but adaptable to needs of a specific CRISMA Application. Thus, they should provide convenient configuration mechanisms and well-defined extension points.
2. Building Block Software Components must implement the functionalities that are marked as mandatory in the functional descriptions and specifications of the respective Functional Building Blocks.
3. Building Block Software Components should implement the functionalities that are marked as optional in the functional descriptions and specifications of the respective Functional Building Blocks.
4. Building Block Software Components that are implemented from scratch and thus not based on an existing Software Candidates must provide their user interface(s) as composite UI Modules.

5. Building Block Software Components that are implemented from scratch must use the following parts of the Development Infrastructure described in APPENDIX (i):
 - Project and Infrastructure Hosting
 - Source code Management System
 - Progress and Milestone Management System
 - Issue Management System

6. Building Block Software Components that are implemented from scratch should use the following parts of the Development Infrastructure described in APPENDIX (i):
 - Build Automation System
 - Continuous Integration System
 - Dependency Management System
 - Release Management System

7. Building Block Software Components that are implemented on basis of existing Software Candidates must use the following parts of the Development Infrastructure described in APPENDIX (i):
 - Progress and Milestone Management System
 - Issue Management System

8. Building Block Software Components that are implemented on basis of existing Software Candidates should use the following parts of the Development Infrastructure described in APPENDIX (i):
 - Release Management System

3.3. Rules for version numbering

In the CRISMA project partners, developing software components shall use proper versioning, which means that any piece of software that will be made available to other partners must be uniquely identified by a unique version number. If a specific version number has been assigned to a piece of software, it is called a release version. The release version and the software released under it may never be changed again. If the software requires further changes (because of new features added, bugs fixed, etc.) a new release version shall be produced.

The version number shall be attached to the release artefact name (the release jar, the release JavaScript, etc.). A release artefact's name shall be build as follows:

- <artifact_name>: the name of the artefact, e.g. crisma-http-tools
- <artifact_version>: the release version of the artefact, e.g. 1.28.4
- <artifact_classifier>: an optional artefact classifier, e.g. en
- <file_extension>: the file extension reflecting the file type, e.g. js

Scheme:

`<artifact_name>-<artifact_version>[-<artifact_classifier>].<file_extension>`
e.g. `crisma-http-tools-1.28.4-en.js`

The numbering scheme for release versions is described in the chapter 3.3.2.

3.3.1. Making releases

Any partner performing a release shall create a tag in the Source code Management System (git repository) that marks the state of the repository which reflects the release version of the software. The tag shall be named `<artefact_name>-<artefact_version>`.

In case of the release of an actual file it shall be done as described in the chapter 3.3.2.

3.3.2. Version numbering scheme proposal

Scheme: “`<major>.<minor>.<bugfix>`”, e.g. “3.15.1”

`<major>` changes: fundamental interface changes, most likely no backwards compatibility, long-term release cycles

`<minor>` changes: no to few interface changes, backwards compatible, mostly changed/additional features and bug fixes, short- to mid-term release cycles

`<bugfix>` changes: critical bug fixes only, that severely affect the stability of a currently running system and need immediate delivery. This includes bugfix updates of dependencies.

In case of newly developed software the versioning shall begin with “0.1.0”. The minor version shall be increased for new features and shall reach “1.0.0” as soon as the API can be considered stable.

For more information on this, see <http://semver.org>

4. Rules for Information Models

Those are rules for the specification of Control and Communication Information Models (CCIMs).

4.1. Formal Specification

1. All CCIMs must be modelled and formally specified in Unified Modelling Language (UML). The UML specification of CCIMs serves as formal documentation for the Implementation Architecture (D32.2) as well as reference for API developers.
2. The actual CCIM data (CCIM Entities) that is exposed through a RESTful API has to be encoded in the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) (RFC4627) data format.
3. The UML to JSON mapping is not supported by mapping tools but has to be performed by API developers during the specification and design of the RESTful API. Apart from a few rules, this mapping is subject to interpretation of the API developer.
4. The RESTful APIs as well as the REST (JSON) models that are based on the CCIM UML models must be formally specified using the Swagger API Documentation Toolkit as described in Rules and Best Practices for API Specifications (chapter 5).
5. Besides the mandatory JSON encoding other optional representations of CCIM Entities, e.g. in XML, may be supported by a specific implementation of an REST API.

4.2. Rules for CCIMs

The following rules and recommendations for CCIM modelling apply both to UML models as well as to JSON models. As already mentioned before, the JSON models are another representation of the UML models for a specific data encoding format. A CCIM class defines the schema of a CCIM Entity, thus a CCIM Entity is an instance of a CCIM Class.

1. A whole CCIM may consist of several CCIM Classes.
2. All CCIM classes should be derived from one base class, which defines the common properties id, domain, name and description.
3. Properties of a CCIM class must consist of atomic types (integer, string, boolean, ...), arrays and other CCIM Classes only.
4. Collections of CCIM entities must be represented by simple arrays, associative arrays (maps) are not supported.
5. Complex relationship like many to many relationships or cyclic relationship between classes should be avoided.
6. camelCase should be used when naming properties, underscores shall be omitted.

7. When defining CCIM Classes the plural form shall be used, e.g. worldstates instead of worldstate.
8. The ISO 8601 standard should be used to encode date and time. UTC should be used for dates.

There are also a few rules and recommendations which are specific to the JSON representation (REST Model) of CCIMS Entities. Since this JSON representation is related to the resource-oriented architecture (ROA) and REST APIs, respectively, the terminology of the ROA is used to describe classes and instances. A CCIM Class in the context of a REST (JSON) Model is therefore called Resource Type or Resource Class and a CCIM Entity is called Resource Object, Resource Instance or just Resource.

Figure 2: Mapping UML Models to REST Models

4.3. Rules for JSON Models

The following rules and recommendations apply to REST (JSON) Models:

1. Supplemental properties which are not part of the originating UML Model but are added to a Resource Type of the REST Model must be prefixed with a dollar sign, e.g. *\$ref*, *\$self*, etc. Those supplemental properties shall be in the following order: First come *\$ref* or *\$self* properties, then any other *\$*-prefixed properties and at last all

properties defined by the originating UML Model in the order they were specified in the UML Model.

2. Many-to-Many relationships between two Resource Types (classes) should be represented by a dedicated Resource Type that models those relationships.
3. In addition to the properties defined by a CCIM Class, a resource instance has an additional and mandatory `$self` property which contains the relative URI of the resource instance (self reference). The contents of the `$self` property must match the API path component of the location HTTP header field, e.g.
location=`http://someserver.com:8118/crsima/ICMM/v2/classes/earthquake.worldstate/31337`, `$self="/classes/earthquake.worldstate/31337"`
4. References to other resources have to be expressed according to (json-reference) with help of the `$ref` property which contains a URI (RFC3986), that identifies the location of the JSON object being referenced. The `$ref` property is also a relative URI.
5. Collection resources (collections of complex resources) have to be represented by an array of JSON values that either contain resources instances or references to resources instances. Links to resource instances have to be represented by `$ref` properties. Additionally, a collection resource object has to define the properties `$offset`, `$limit`, `$first`, `$previous`, `$next` and `$last` to navigate through paginated collection resources.
 - a. `$offset` defines the actual offset in a paginated collection
 - b. `$limit` defines the maximum number of distinct entries in a paginated collection
 - c. `$first` provides a relative URI to the first page of a paginated collection, e.g. `"$first": "/my.persons?offset=0&limit=100"`. `$first` must always be specified.
 - d. `$last` provides a relative URI to the last page of a paginated collection, e.g. `"$last": "/my.persons?offset=300&limit=100"`. `$last` must always be specified.
 - e. `$prev` provides a relative URI to the previous page of a paginated collection. `$prev` must not be specified if the current page is identical to `$first`.
 - f. `$next` provides a relative URI to the next page of a paginated collection. `$next` must not be specified if the current page is identical to `$last`.

5. Rules for RESTful API Specifications

Those are rules for the specification and implementation of RESTful APIs.

5.1. Formal Specification

For the formal specification of REST APIs the Swagger API Documentation Toolkit shall be used: "Swagger is a specification and complete framework implementation for describing, producing, consuming, and visualizing RESTful web services. With Swagger's declarative resource specification, clients can understand and consume services without knowledge of server implementation or access to the server code. The Swagger UI framework allows both developers and non-developers to interact with the API in a sandbox UI that gives clear insight into how the API responds to parameters and options." <https://developers.helloverb.com/swagger/>

REST APIs documented and visualised with the Swagger Framework can be easily tested by client developers and even by end users or pilot partners who want to learn about the technical details and capabilities of the Building Blocks exposing the API. Usage of the Swagger Framework is mandatory for all new REST APIs developed in WP34.

5.2. Rules and Best Practices

There are many best practices to be followed when designing and implementing REST APIs. Describing them all in detail would go beyond the scope of this document. Nevertheless, those are the most important rules and recommendations for the specification of RESTful APIs in CRISMA:

1. Each resource has a global lifetime unique ID. Resources types (classes) which represent the schema of a resource are uniquely identified by their canonical name which consist of the name of the application domain (e.g. earthquake, laquila, nordicpilot, etc.) and the name of the resources class (e.g. worldstate) separated by a dot (e.g. earthquake.worldstates). Resource instances (objects) are uniquely identified by the id of their class (domain.class) and a key that is defined by the underlying service implementation (e.g. table key, UUID, ...). This unique id is also part of the URI of the resource. Therefore it has to be present in the location header of the server response and in `$self` property of the resource object or class.
2. The server response shall always provide the HTTP Header field '`Location`' containing the absolute URI (with host) of the resource. Each resource object returned by the API shall provide a "`$self`" property containing the relative URI of the resource. Further rules for mandatory properties of resource objects are defined by the rules and guidelines for CCIMs (section 4.3).
3. If the API supports different output formats (content encoding) of the same resource (e.g. JSON, XML, CSV), the resource format returned by the API shall be determined by the order of HTTP accept headers provided by the client. Alternatively, the API should support resource name extensions to determine the format requested by the client. E.g. `resource.json` returns the JSON representation of the resource while

resource.csv returns the CSV representation of the resource. The mandatory resource format to be supported by a any CRISMA API is JSON. Thus, the default behaviour of the API when no accept header and no resource name extensions is provided is to return the JSON representation of the resource.

The API documentation shall inform about the output formats supported by the API.

4. We distinguish between collection resources and instance resources. Collection and instance resources are referenced by the canonical name of their resource type. /\$domain.\$class/ shall be used for access to a collection of all resources of this type and /\$domain.\$class/\$key shall be used for access to a specific instance resource, e.g. GET /earthquake.worldstates/ returns all worldstate resource objects of the earthquake domain while GET/ earthquake.worldstates/aabb returns just the worldstate object 'aabb'.
5. HTTP operations are mapped to CRUD (create, read, update delete) in the following way:
 - a. GET shall be used for read operations. The HTTP header of a GET response should optionally contain a *Link* header field with relation type "describedBy" that points to the type definition (class) of a resource instance, e.g. <http://example.com/ICMM/v2/classes/ earthquake.worldstates>; rel="describedBy"
 - b. DELETE shall be used for delete operations
 - c. PUT and POST shall be used for update and create operations.
 - i. PUT can be used for create whereby the unique id of the resource must be known by client beforehand (e.g. PUT /earthquake.worldstates/aabbc).
 - ii. POST can be used for create whereby the unique id of the resource does not have to be known beforehand (e.g. POST /earthquake.worldstates/).The id of the newly created resource instance must be part of server response (location header field).
 - iii. PUT and POST can be used for **full update** operations. In case of a full update the complete resource object must be send to the server regardless how many properties have changed. Update operations have to be executed against the URI of a particular resource instance, e.g. /earthquake.worldstates/aabbc.
 - iv. PUT and POST can also be used for **partial updates**. A partial update may send a JSON object containing only changed resource properties.
6. Deleting specific properties of a resource is considered as a special case of a partial update. It has to be realised by a PUT or POST request whereby the properties to be deleted are set to NULL.

7. GET, DELETE and PUT are idempotent operations, thus repeated calls shall result in the same server state, especially if PUT is used for full or partial updates.
8. A full or partial update or a create issued via PUT or POST method may return the complete modified or created resource object because the server could alter timestamps, version numbers, etc. of the resource object; therefore always the freshest instance of the modified resource should be made available to the client. This behaviour can be controlled by the optional query parameter *requestResultingInstance {true|false}*.
The API documentation shall inform about the default behaviour when no *requestResultingInstance* parameter is provided.
9. For all GET, POST, PUT, DELTE operations, the server shall always return
 - a. correct and verbose HTTP Status codes in the HTTP header, e.g. 201 created;
 - b. the location header which contains the full URI of the resource; and
 - c. the correct media type, e.g. *application/json* for JSON resources.
10. APIs should be versioned and backwards compatible to previous versions. Major versions should become part of the API URI (e.g. */api/v2/*). Optionally, the client may appended the requested version to the media-type property in the HTTP header, e.g. *application/json;application&v=1*.
The API documentation shall provide information about the current version and backwards compatibility to previous versions.
11. When the API is queried to return complex resource objects (that are resources containing nested resources), the complex resource object may contain only the references of the nested resources. A resource reference is defined by (resource-ref) as "*\$ref*" property that contains the relative URI of the resource. It is up to the client to resolve those linked resources. The same behaviour applies also to collection resources, e.g. a request to */earthquake.worldstates/* may return the stubs of all worldstate objects of the earthquake domain.
The API documentation shall inform about the default behaviour whether complete or lightweight complex resource objects are returned.
12. A client may also control the behaviour of the API whether complete complex resource objects or lightweight complex resource objects consisting of references to nested resource objects shall be provided. This behaviour can be controlled by the optional *expand* and *level* query parameters which are appended to the GET resource request.
 - a. The *expand* parameter has as value a list of comma separated resource property names. If a property points to a complex resource, the resource shall be expanded by the server.
 - b. The *level* parameter has as value a positive integer that determines the lowest level to which resources are expanded.

- c. Expand and level parameters can be combined
- d. If the expand parameter is provided and the level parameter is omitted, resources matching the expand properties are expanded to the lowest level
- e. If the level parameter is provided and the expand parameter is omitted, any resources are expanded up to the level specified by the level parameter
- f. If the expand parameter is omitted and the level parameter is set to -1, the API shall return a fully expanded resource.

The API documentation shall inform whether those parameters are supported or not and what the default behaviour of the API regarding resource expansion is when those parameters are not supported or not provided.

13. The client may also request the API to return partial resource objects. Therefore, the client appends the *fields* request parameter to the GET resource request and specifies in a comma-separated list of only those properties of the resource the client is interested in. Please note, that this mechanism is only supported for top-level resource objects and the reduction is not applied on nested resources. The *fields* request parameter can be used in combination with the expand request parameter, though. This mechanism shall not be applied to the *\$self* field which is mandatory for all resource objects.

The API documentation shall inform whether the API supports the provision of partial resource objects.

14. The representation of resource objects containing null values should be controllable by the *omitNullProperties* parameter that can be used in a GET request. If the parameter is set to true, properties that have a null value shall not be present in the returned resource object.

The API documentation shall inform whether this parameter is supported or not.

15. The amount of resource objects returned by queries to collection resources should be controllable by the *offset* and *limit* query parameters. Thereby, *limit* specifies the maximum number of resources returned by one GET resource request to the collection resources and *offset* the offset in the entire list resources available in the particular collection. In addition to the array of resource objects or resource links collection resources shall contain a set of specific fields which provide links to navigate through the collection. (see also rules and guidelines for CCIMs, section 4.3).

The API documentation shall inform whether those parameters are supported or not and what their default values are.

16. Error messages should be as descriptive as possible and should provide as much information as possible to trace back the error. Besides the correct HTTP status codes (404, 409, 500, ...) in the HTTP header, in case of an error the API shall also return a specific error resource object which contains detailed information on the cause of the error. Thereby, the error message must not contain security sensitive information like password, etc.

6. Rules for UI Integration and Development

The following rules apply to the development of Composite UI Modules and the related UI Integration and UI Mashup Platform. Rationales and explanations of the rules are given in APPENDIX (ii) which defines also the revised UI Integration Approach of the CRISMA Functional Architecture and introduces the new Building Block of the UI Integration Platform.

6.1. Rules for Composite UI Modules

1. Each Composite UI Module shall be realised as distinct website, which consists of a static part (HTML/CSS + other static resources) defining layout and structure of the user interface and a dynamic part (JavaScript) providing dynamic content and interaction functionalities.
2. Composite UI Modules must be implemented in HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript (ECMA 262).
3. Composite UI Modules must not rely on any type of external plug-ins like Oracle Java, Adobe Flash, Microsoft Silverlight, and others.
4. Composite UI Modules shall be realised as purely client-side and server-agnostic solution that does not require any specific server-side infrastructure (e.g. enterprise application server, servlet container, portal server, ...) apart from the Infrastructure Building Blocks provides by the CRISMA Framework (e.g. ICMM, UI Mashup Platform for Mashable Composite UI Modules, etc.).
5. Composite UI Modules should not rely on proprietary APIs or services that pose the risk of exposing security and privacy sensitive information to third parties.
6. Composite UI Modules shall expose their programmatically accessible functionality via a JavaScript API.
7. As any other Federates, Composite UI Modules shall support bidirectional communication with the ICMM. Specifically, Composite UI Modules must be able to receive action requests or event notifications dispatched by the ICMM. Thereby, appropriate transport techniques like WebSockets, Server-sent Events or long polling shall be supported by Composite UI Module.
8. A Composite UI Module must provide a self-description that informs about its capabilities. Specifically, this self-description has to be provided as JSON-encoded CCIM and has to contain general descriptive and technical meta-information as well as a description of the Composite UI Modules' JavaScript API.
9. The UI Integration Platform must be able to render and execute Composite UI Modules. Thus, it must support HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript.
10. A Mashable Composite UI Module must be able to interact with the UI Mashup Platform or other Mashable Composite UI Modules through the Mashup JavaScript API, which is provided by the UI Mashup Platform.

11. The UI Mashup Platform shall support to interactively compose Mashable Composite UI Modules and Integrated Widgets to rich internet applications.
12. Mashable Composite UI Modules should be based upon Composite UI Modules, which can be used independently of a particular UI Mashup Platform in a CRISMA Application.
13. Communication and Interaction between Mashable Composite UI Modules among each other and between the UI Mashup Platform should be based upon functions exposed by the JavaScript API of wrapped Composite UI Modules.
14. The UI Integration Platform should be able to interact with Composite UI Modules via their JavaScript API.
15. The UI Integration Platform should be able to interact with Mashable Composite UI Modules that are assembled in a UI Mashup Platform. This interaction should be performed either via the JavaScript API of the Composite UI Modules that have been wrapped into Mashable Composite UI Modules or via APIs of the respective UI Mashup Platform.
16. The business logic of Composite UI Modules that need to perform demanding and long-running processes should be encapsulated in a dedicated server-side component.

7. Rules for JavaScript APIs

As described in the previous chapter, Composite UI Modules shall expose a JavaScript API that can be accessed by the UI Integration Platform, possibly also other Composite UI Modules. There are currently no specific rules for the design of such an API apart from the general rule that the Google JavaScript Language Rules and the JavaScript Style Guide¹ (ref) shall be followed when developing JavaScript APIs and Composite UI Modules in general. Especially the rules for documentation of functions with JSDoc² and exception handling are important.

¹ <https://google-styleguide.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/javascriptguide.xml>

² <https://google-styleguide.googlecode.com/svn/trunk/javascriptguide.xml?showone=Comments#Comments>

8. References

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<http://git-scm.com/>

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<http://jenkins-ci.org/>

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APPENDIX (i) Development Platform

In order to increase productivity and interoperability of developers CRISMA defines a development infrastructure. Such an infrastructure provides tools and procedures to cover all aspects of modern software development such as

- Build automation: “Build automation is the act of scripting or automating a wide variety of tasks that software developers do in their day-to-day activities [...]”³
- Continuous integration: “Continuous integration (CI) is the practice, in software engineering, of merging all developer workspaces with a shared mainline several times a day.”⁴
- Dependency management: In modern programming software is hardly developed from scratch but relies on a number of other pieces of software. Such a relationship is called a dependency. These dependencies have to be managed somehow to ensure every developer working on the same software uses the same dependencies. Additionally they have to be made accessible through an online repository. See also [Dependency \(computer science\)](#).
- Issue management: “An issue tracking system (also ITS, trouble ticket system, support ticket or incident ticket system) is a computer software package that manages and maintains lists of issues, as needed by an organization”⁵
- Progress and milestone management: Project managers need to track progress of the software development and should mark certain critical parts of a development phase in order to take corrective actions, etc. Thus, some kind of progress and milestone management is needed. Often Issue management provides simple means to do so.
- Release management: “Release management is the process of managing software releases from development stage to software release.”⁶
- Revision control: “Revision control, also known as version control and source control (and an aspect of software configuration management), is the management of changes to documents, computer programs, large web sites, and other collections of information.”⁷
- Project and infrastructure hosting: Without hosting, none of the above-mentioned aspects can be covered.

³ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Build_automation

⁴ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Continuous_integration

⁵ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Issue_tracking_system

⁶ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Release_management

⁷ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Source_code_management

Proposed tools

cismet proposes the use the following tools in order to cover the continuous integration aspects:

- **Apache Maven** [MAVEN]
is used for the management of software projects and provides a so called build lifecycle. The build lifecycle encompasses for example to process resources, compile sources, package results, retrieve project dependencies (e.g. external libraries) and release software bundle. It mainly covers Build automation and Dependency management and is able to do the actual release of a piece of software.
- **Jfrog Artifactory** [ARTIFACTORY]
is an artefact repository and is used to manage software artefacts and provides caching capabilities for external repositories. It is compatible to the major dependency management tools such as maven, ivy and gradle. It also integrates well with the Jenkins CI Server.
- **Jenkins CI Server** [JENKINS]
is used for continuous integration, which means it continuously integrates changes in the source code, performs the specified automated test runs and deploys changes to the software repository (Artifactory) and other relevant targets.
- **git** [GIT]
is used for revision control and keeps track of source code changes.
- **GitHub** [GITHUB]
is used as a public online source code repository as well as for issue tracking and management and provides change logs.

Choosing tools

In CRISMA different development approaches will be taken dependent on the initial situation of the partners. There will be the customisation of already existing software as well as complete new developments. Additionally there are different topics of development that are relevant, which is the development of:

- Composite UI Modules and JavaScript APIs
- REST APIs
- New Software Components

Regardless of the kind or topic of software to be developed any partner is obliged to apply proper release management.

It is important to note, that customisation of existing software is not covered by the development infrastructure proposed herein apart from the development of UI Modules and CRISMA APIs, which may be part of the customisation activities.

Figure 3: Mapping of development approaches to the development infrastructure

Composite UI Modules and JavaScript APIs

Any Composite UI Module consists of HTML and JavaScript. A JavaScript API is either a separate JavaScript Library providing common functionalities which can be embedded into a Composite UI Module or it is part of the Composite UI Module itself and exposes some functionality to the enclosing environment (e.g. to a Mashup platform or a web browser).

Any partner developing such modules and JS APIs shall use git for revision control as well as GitHub for hosting and issue management. This way it is guaranteed that all partners have access to the software and may directly reference resources (e.g. common JS libraries) without hosting them themselves. Moreover, it is easy for every partner to report any issues referencing specific revisions, etc.

CRISMA REST APIs

Developers of CRISMA REST APIs are not restricted to any tool. A REST API is typically exposed as HTTP web service whereby the actual implementation of the web service (as Java Servlet, as PHP script, as part of an existing application, ...) is

However, API developers they shall provide a related GitHub project for issue management so that partners can keep track of and discuss ongoing development, may request API changes, etc. Please note that we consider the development of an API as extension of an existing software component to make it CRISMA-aware. The development of the API as part of the development a completely a new software component is covered in the next section.

New Software Components

Any new Software Components shall use git for revision control as well as GitHub for hosting and issue management. Moreover, an online repository has to be made available so that other partners are able to access those software components and may reuse them. Though

not necessary, it is highly recommended to adopt the proposed Software Development Infrastructure as described in the following. As cismet uses this very infrastructure any partners who do not want to or are not able to set it up by themselves cismet may provide hosting services.

Figure 4: Software Development Infrastructure Interaction shows the interaction of the proposed components. During the development process, maven is responsible to retrieve all the project source's dependencies that are needed to compile the project. To do so maven uses the Artifactory repository. Artifactory serves as an artefact repository for all the software developed in the CRISMA project but also retrieves and caches third party artefacts.

When new code is checked in by the developer Jenkins will be notified about the change thus starting a build of the project and all its relationships. After a successful build, the project artefact will be automatically deployed to the Artifactory repository.

Figure 4: Software Development Infrastructure Interaction

Project builds and automated tests can be managed and monitored via the Jenkins web interface as shown in *Figure 5: Jenkins Continuous Integration Web Interface*.

Figure 5: Jenkins Continuous Integration Web Interface

The integration environment does not only ease development significantly, it also provides means for testing the software. Therefore automated unit tests are specified which ensure the developed software does what it is intended to do from the perspective of the developer. It does however not ensure that the software behaves as expected by the users which were involved in the specification of the requirements and thus the functionalities of the software.. The results of the automated unit test are documented as part of the build history of the software projects and can be accessed through the Jenkins web interface (*Figure 5: Jenkins Continuous Integration Web Interface*)

APPENDIX (ii) Revised UI Integration Approach

This chapter will eventually replace the UI Integration Approach defined in the first version of the CRISMA Functional Architecture (D32.1, 2013). It describes a revised UI Integration approach that takes also the capabilities of modern UI Integration and UI Mashup Platforms into account.

According to (D32.1, 2013) *“the basic concept of the UI integration approach in CRISMA is to create web applications that expose CRISMA web based Composite UI Modules for arbitrary browser environments.”* The related design decision on the overall GUI approach to be followed in CRISMA states *“new CRISMA GUIs shall be developed as mark-up-based and client-based web applications using common web technologies like HTML5 and AJAX. Those GUI components must be modular and composable in order to be able to combine them into one overall e.g. mobile or desktop application or to integrate them into existing applications.”* This design decision is also the fundamental rule for composite UI Modules.

This design decision is also the basis for the fundamental rule of composite UI Modules:

Each Composite UI Module shall be realised as distinct website, which consists of a static part (HTML/CSS + other static resources) defining layout and structure of the user interface and a dynamic part (JavaScript) providing dynamic content and interaction functionalities.

Additional rules are needed to ensure technical interoperability and composability, especially regarding the UI Integration Platform and the UI Mashup Platform. The complete set of rules for composite UI Modules is presented in the following sections.

There are few technical requirements that set the boundaries for the development of Composite UI Modules and the Integration Platform Building Block. Of course, since composite UI Modules and the UI Integration Platform are by definition CRISMA Federates, all technical and interoperability requirements on CRISMA Federates apply also to Composite UI Modules and the UI Integration and Mashup Platforms. Technically, and as shown in Figure 6,

Composite UI Modules must be implemented in HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript.

Figure 6: Composite UI Module Overview

Accordingly, we can also define what Composite UI Modules are not made of:

Composite UI Modules must not rely on any type of external plug-ins like Oracle Java, Adobe Flash, Microsoft Silverlight, and others.

Additionally, Composite UI Modules must be standalone and self-contained, which means they must not rely on a certain server infrastructure in the backend to function properly.

Composite UI Modules shall be realised as purely client-side and server-agnostic solution that does not require any specific backend server-side infrastructure (e.g. enterprise application server, servlet container, portal server, ...) services or components apart from the Infrastructure services Building Blocks provides by the CRISMA Framework (e.g. ICMM, UI Mashup Platform for Mashable Composite UI Modules, etc.).

More precisely, a Composite UI Module is a static HTML page and its dynamic behaviour is realised entirely by HTML5 and AJAX techniques in conjunction with CRISMA APIs (e.g. the ICMM APIs). Techniques that rely on server-generated dynamic content like Portlets, Servlets, PHP Scripts, etc. are not suitable for the implementation of Composite UI Modules. Moreover, a Composite UI Module should also operate properly when loaded from the local file system involving no HTTP web server whatsoever.

Furthermore, and especially in regard to security sensitive and information exchanged within a CRISMA Application, the usage of proprietary and vendor-specific APIs (e.g. Google APIs, Yahoo APIs, ...) by a Composite UI Module is strongly discouraged. Although not a rule, the following recommendation is given:

Composite UI Modules should not rely on proprietary APIs or services that pose the risk of exposing security and privacy sensitive information to third parties.

Whether such a service or API is save to be used has to be decided on a case by basis by the architects and developers of the respective CRISMA Application. While it might be o.k. to

use the Google Maps API for displaying background maps, storing sensitive information in cloud service like Dropbox or Google Drive might be in violation to data protection rules or non-disclosure agreements.

Since Composite UI Modules may also provide functionalities that can be called by other Composite UI Modules or even other types of components, there is a need for a well-defined API exposed by each Composite UI Module. However, in contrary to the initial GUI integration concept presented in (D32.1, 2013) this API shall not be realised as RESTful API. Since pure HTML components are not able to offer such a RESTful API it would have to be provided by a separate server side component. The outdated composite UI Modules interaction concept shown in Figure 7 is therefore no longer valid and is replaced by a more flexible approach, which is based on JavaScript and ICMM APIs.

According to Figure 7, Composite UI Modules should be split into a client-side and a server side part. The server-side part would expose a REST API that accepts incoming calls from other components, which want to call functions of the Composite UI Module. Thus, besides the creation of HTML, CSS and JavaScript snippets the development of a Composite UI Module would also include the implementation of a RESTful service that can be deployed on a web server.

Since the implementation of such an additional server-side component would place an unnecessary burden on developers, integrators and maintainers of a CRISMA Application, the second iteration of the CRISMA Framework Architecture introduces an improved interaction concept for Composite UI Modules.

However, one must realise that in some cases a server-side component for encapsulating the business logic of a Composite UI Module might be required. For those either cases, the ICMM Actions API or an Extension API can be used to outsource time and resource-demanding tasks (see Figure 16). In consequence, we can state that

- it is o.k. to split a Composite UI Module into a server-side and a client-side part when the role of the server-side part is to encapsulate business logic of the Composite UI Module; and
- it is not o.k. to split a Composite UI Module into a server-side and a client-side part when the role of the server-side part is provide an endpoint for other components to communicate and interact with the Composite UI Module.

Figure 7: Outdated Composite UI Modules Interaction Concept

For communication and interaction with Composite UI Modules, a new concept has been introduced. This concept is based on the fact that web pages are able to call JavaScript functions of other web pages acting in the same scope (e.g. in the same web browser window). Furthermore, a HTML/JavaScript engine (e.g. a web browser) is also able to call JavaScript functions of the web pages it is rendering. Therefore, a further rule for Composite UI Modules can be defined:

Composite UI Modules shall expose their programmatically accessible functionality via a JavaScript API.

However, in some cases a component that wants to interact with a Composite UI Module may not have the possibility or capability to invoke JavaScript functions. In this case, an alternative possibility is provided by the ICMM. The ICMM Action and Event Delegation APIs can be used to forward arbitrary action requests to a Composite UI Module that is registered with the ICMM. Figure 8 shows how different types of components can interact with the Composite UI Modules' JavaScript API.

Figure 8: Improved Composite UI Modules Interaction Concept

Depending on its capabilities, a Federated Component may use either the mandatory Composite UI Modules' JavaScript API or the ICMM Action REST API to interact with the Composite UI Module. An Integrated Component, which is not aware of any ICMM API, may only interact with the Composite UI Modules through the JavaScript API. Please note that in this case Composite UI Module and Integrated Component must reside in the same scope, e.g. the same web page or the same web browser window.

An important prerequisite for communicating via the optional Action API is the ability of the Composite UI Module to accept and answer incoming request sent by a web server. In principle, there exist two techniques for realising this kind of server-induced communication with HTML/JavaScript based web clients: Web Sockets and Server-Sent Events (SSE). While Web Sockets natively support bidirectional communication through a two-way communication channel SSE connections can only push data from the web server to the client. However, there exist client- and server-side frameworks like the Atmosphere Framework (ref) which provide transparent bidirectional client-server communication regardless of underlying transport technique. Even fall back transport like long-polling can be enabled if the client cannot accept incoming request at all. In any case, bidirectional communication between the ICMM and CRISMA Federates is a key requirement for event notifications (Event API) and action requests (Action API). Therefore, also this requirement applies to Composite UI Modules:

As any other Federates, Composite UI Modules shall support bidirectional communication with the ICMM. Specifically, Composite UI Modules must be able to receive action requests or event notifications dispatched by the ICMM. Thereby, appropriate transport techniques like Web Sockets, Server-sent Events or long polling shall be supported by Composite UI Module.

It is important to note that the ICMM Action API is a generic API for executing arbitrary actions in the context of the ICMM and each action has to be implemented for each Composite UI Modules communication. Moreover, the approach of action delegation through the ICMM is considered as a workaround when no JavaScript Communication with Composite UI Modules is possible.

The ICMM Action API can also be used in conjunction with the Event Delegation API to forward action requests to Composite UI Modules. The Event Delegation API is realized by the Publish/Subscribe Context Broker Infrastructure Building Block. The Publish/Subscribe Context Broker is used by the ICMM to delegate events to CRISMA Federates. Thereby, a CRISMA Federate can be notified once a new CCIM entity of a specific type is created, deleted or updated in the respective ICMM repository. However, the Publish/Subscribe Context Broker can also be triggered by the Action API to delegate action requests to respective Federates.

Another general rule for Federates that has to be slightly extended when applied to Composite UI Modules is the rule for self-describing components:

A Composite UI Module has to provide a self-description that informs about its capabilities. Specifically, this self-description has to be provided as JSON-encoded CCIM and has to contain general descriptive and technical meta-information as well as a description of the Composite UI Modules' JavaScript API.

Having formulated those basic rules for the realization and behaviour of Composite UI Modules, we can now discuss how Composite UI Modules can be embedded or composed into whole CRISMA Applications. Ideally, the GUI of a CRISMA Application is composed entirely of Composite UI Modules. However, the GUI integration approach of the CRISMA Framework Architecture takes also into account that a CRISMA Application may be based upon existing non-CRISMA-aware GUIs and possibly also a mixture of Composite UI Modules and existing GUIs. Therefore, the concepts and Building Blocks, respectively, of the UI Integration and UI Mashup Platform were introduced.

The UI Integration Platform is a client-side component for displaying Composite UI Modules. A technical requirement and basic rule for this UI Integration Platform is:

The UI Integration Platform must be able to render and execute Composite UI Modules. Thus, it must support HTML5, CSS3 and JavaScript.

Figure 9: UI Integration Platform Basic Overview

Technically, this basic requirement is met by most modern web browsers as they implement the respective rendering and execution engines (Figure 9).

In consequence, the GUI of a CRISMA Application may be realized as browser-based rich internet application (RIA). Nevertheless, additional requirements on the UI Integration Platform arise when Composite UI Modules shall be able to interact with other types of existing GUIs or even be embedded into existing GUIs. Before going further into detail, additional aspects when building RIAs have to be considered first.

Those are the aspects of modularity and composability. Composite UI Modules are self-contained and modular by itself. As mentioned before different Composite UI Modules must yet be composed to form one whole application. Although there are several techniques and frameworks for building modularized RIAs, an overall concept and a separate Building Block that seamlessly fits into the CRISMA Framework Architecture had to be defined – the UI Mashup Platform. The UI Mashup Platform is a server-side layout container and execution environment for interactively composing (mashing up) HTML widgets (Figure 10).

Figure 10: UI Mashup Platform Basic Overview

The UI Mashup Platform provides auxiliary functions exposed as JavaScript APIs, further one referred to as Mashup APIs. Among others, this Mashup APIs can be consumed by widgets to leverage communication with widgets among each other or with the platform itself. Following the concept of CRISMA-aware (federated) Components that are able to interact with the CRISMA Middleware Infrastructure (ICMM) through its RESTful API we introduce the concept of “Mashable” Composite UI Modules that are aware of the Mashup JavaScript APIs.

A Mashable Composite UI Modules must be able to interact with the UI Mashup Platform or other Mashable Composite UI Modules through the Mashup JavaScript APIs, which are provided by the UI Mashup Platform.

Likewise, the general rule for the UI Mashup Platform is:

The UI Mashup Platform shall support to interactively compose Mashable Composite UI Modules and Integrated Widgets to rich internet applications.

Interactively means, that a graphical designer tool for creating the overall application layout and for connecting (“wiring”) widgets should be provided by the UI Mashup Platform. Otherwise, there would be no real benefit compared to an ordinary RIA framework.

Mashable Composite UI Modules shall also inform the UI Mashup Platform about their composability with other widgets. This rule is already covered by the general rule of self-description. However, the format of the self-description (capabilities) expected by a particular UI Mashup Platform (e.g. XML Widget Description Language⁸, portlet.xml, etc.) may be different from the capabilities JSON document provided by an ordinary Composite UI Module. In addition, the interaction between widgets may have to be realized with help of UI Mashup Platform specific methods instead of the JavaScript API and ICMM Action API. These are potential conflicts; therefore, the distinction between Composite UI Modules and Mashable Composite UI Modules and their relationships to the UI Integration and the UI Mashup Platform respectively is an important aspect to be considered.

While a Composite UI Module may exist independently of a particular UI Integration Platform (e.g. not bound to a specific web browser or web server), a Mashable Composite UI Module is always depended on a certain UI Mashup Platform (e.g. a portal server like Liferay or an actual widget mashup platform like Wirecloud).

The CRISMA Framework intends to deliver generic and composable Building Blocks. However, it is not guaranteed that every CRISMA Application will use the UI Mashup Platform Building Block or a specific implementation of this Building Block. Therefore, the following rule is introduced:

Mashable Composite UI Module should be based upon Composite UI Modules, that can be used independently of a particular UI Mashup Platform in a CRISMA Application.

In consequence, a Mashable Composite UI Module should be implemented first as (non-mashable) Composite UI Module and then wrapped into a Mashable Composite UI Module (Figure 11). How this wrapping is performed depends on the particular UI Mashup Platform Implementation. The UI Mashup Platform Implementation of the Implementation Architecture of the CRISMA Framework is the Wirecloud Platform. In principle, functionalities required by the enclosing UI Mashup Platform on Mashable Composite UI Modules, e.g. for being able to connect (wiring) widgets, should be mapped to the JavaScript API of the Composite UI Module.

Communication and Interaction between Mashable Composite UI Modules among each other and between the UI Mashup Platform should be based upon functions exposed by the JavaScript API of wrapped Composite UI Modules.

⁸ <http://conwet.fi.upm.es/docs/display/wirecloud/XML+Widget+Description+Language>

Figure 11: Wrapping of Composite UI Modules into Mashable Composite UI Modules

Figure 12 brings the concepts of the UI Integration and the UI Mashup Platform into relation to the general terminology of the CRISMA Framework Architecture.

Figure 12: UI Integration Terminology

Interestingly, the UI Mashup Platform may also be used to mash-up Composite UI Modules with other types of widgets. Following the definition of Integrated Components which are not CRISMA-aware but can be integrated into a CRISMA Application, we call such widgets Integrated Widgets.

It is important to note, that the Mashup JavaScript API is by no means a replacement of the RESTful ICMM API but an optional extension that leverages interactive composability (shown also in Figure 11). Mashable Composite UI Modules are by definition CRISMA Federates and as a matter of course all rules and restrictions (see chapter 2), especially regarding the exchange of CCIM with the ICMM, apply also to Composite UI Modules.

Also notably in Figure 12 is, that the realization relationships between UI Integration Platform and UI Mashup Platform, respectively, to the Integration and User Interaction Building Blocks are shown greyed out to highlight a weak relationship. Whether the UI Integration Platform or the UI Mashup Platform have to be realized as Building Block and thus as CRISMA Federate depends on the design of a concrete Application Architecture.

An Application Architecture that defines one central GUI, which is based on the UI Mashup Platform and the widgets contained therein, does not necessarily need a sophisticated federated UI Integration Platform. Since the UI application logic is already covered by the mashed up RIA, a simple web browser will be able to play the role of the UI Integration Platform.

In the opposite case, when a Composite UI Module shall be integrated into an existing application, the UI Integration Platform should be able to support interaction and communication between the existing application and the Composite UI Module. Preferably, via the Composite UI Module's JavaScript API as defined previously (Figure 13).

Figure 13: UI Integration Platform interacting with Composite UI Modules

Furthermore, when several Composite UI Modules shall be integrated into an existing application the UI Mashup Platform should be used to assemble them into one RIA. Consequently, there are several different possibilities for UI Integration and Interaction (Figure 14).

Figure 14: UI Integration and Interaction Possibilities

As consequence, no binding rules on how to actually integrate and assemble Composite UI Modules in UI Integration and the UI Mashup Platform can be given. Instead, the following recommendations are provided:

The UI Integration Platform should be able to interact with Composite UI Modules via their JavaScript API.

The UI Integration Platform should be able to interact with Mashable Composite UI Modules that are assembled in a UI Mashup Platform. This interaction should be performed either via the JavaScript API of the Composite UI Modules that have been wrapped into Mashable Composite UI Modules or via the APIs of the respective UI Mashup Platform.

Another important topic that has already been mentioned but not yet been considered in detail is the fact that web applications should be optimised for responsiveness. Thus, load times, server communication, complex processing of data, etc. should be kept at a minimum. Some CRISMA Building Blocks realised as Composite UI Modules may however require complex business logic. Especially Building blocks dealing with world state transition and simulation model execution possibly need to transfer and process large amounts of data and support fault tolerant and recoverable transactions. Thus, pure web applications are not suited for demanding and long-running processes like managing transitions and starting and monitoring model executions. The business logic for such processes should therefore be executed by a server-side component and exposed via dedicated API.

The business logic of Composite UI Modules that need to perform demanding and long-running processes should be encapsulated in a dedicated server-side component.

There are two possibilities for realising such a server-side component. This first possibility has already been presented in the context of UI Module communication through action delegation (Figure 8). It is based on the ICMM Action API (Figure 15). The Action API is a generic extension point of the ICMM to execute arbitrary actions in the context of the ICMM. Actions are thereby realised as a Java Classes that implement a specific action interface or an abstract class.

/actions		Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations Raw
GET	/actions	Get all actions.
GET	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}	Show and describe an action.
GET	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks	Get all running tasks.
POST	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks	Create a new task of this action.
GET	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks/{taskkey}	Get task status.
DELETE	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks/{taskkey}	Cancel task.
GET	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks/{taskkey}/results	Get task result.
GET	/actions/{domain}.{actionkey}/tasks/{taskkey}/results/{resultkey}	Get task result.

Figure 15: Overview of the ICMM Action API (draft specification)

As can be seen in Figure 15, being a core API of the ICMM the Action API is rather generic and designed to support arbitrary asynchronous tasks.

Figure 16: Composite UI Modules Server-Side Business Logic

If a more fine-grained service interface is needed, the server-side component should be realised by a dedicated RESTful Web Service. Of course, this server-side component should also follow the rules for Building Block Implementations and RESTful APIs. Apart from that, no further rules or guidelines are given since the realisation of this component depends on the business logic of the respective Building Block.